

Exploring and Contrasting Artistic Architectural Elements in Selected Residential Structures throughout Davao City: A Comparative Investigation

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Abstract

This study quantitatively assessed the aesthetic value of selected residential buildings in Davao City and explored the factors influencing aesthetic preferences. Specifically, it aimed to quantify aesthetic scores based on Order and Complexity, compare the results between ancestral and modern houses, and identify the dominant characteristics contributing to their overall aesthetics.

A total of sixty-four (64) residential houses were evaluated, comprising thirty-two (32) Heritage Houses recognized by Museo Dabawenyu and thirty-two (32) Modern Houses, evenly distributed across the three districts of Davao City. The assessment employed Birkhoff's Aesthetic Measure, which considers two primary factors: Order (O) and Complexity (C). The Order factor encompassed six components: symmetry, repetition, equilibrium, disposition, color harmony, and negative factor. Meanwhile, the Complexity factor comprised four components: form complexity, ornaments, silhouette differentiation, and color contrast. Each component was scored on a scale of 0 to 2, and these scores were utilized to compute each house's aesthetic measure (Order/Complexity) for further interpretation.

Findings revealed that both ancestral and modern houses prioritized bilateral symmetry, balanced proportions, and moderate detail complexity. Quantitative results indicated a stronger emphasis on Order rather than Complexity across both house types.

This study contributes to the objective evaluation of residential aesthetics and offers valuable insights for architects and designers in creating visually appealing buildings and living environments.

Keywords: *Aesthetic Measure, aesthetic score, residential houses.*

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Introduction

Understanding why people favor certain buildings involves delving into aesthetics, which encompasses the subjective senses of value provoked by objects. This study utilizes Birkhoff's Aesthetic Measure, a

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mathematical framework for assessing aesthetic value. Birkhoff identifies Aesthetic Measure (M) can be quantified in terms of Order (O) and Complexity (C). On the one hand, Order considers the geometrical relations in a composition involving six (6) components –Symmetry (S), Repetition (R), Equilibrium (E), Disposition (D), Colour Harmony (H), and Randomness or Negative Factor (NF). On the other hand, Complexity (C) is responsible for increasing the effort of attention. It is measured in terms of four (4) components –Form Complexity (CF), Ornaments (ORN), Silhouette Differentiation (SD), and Colour Contrast (CC) (Douchová, 2015). By employing this framework, the study aims to quantify the attributes influencing people’s architectural preferences, drawing from existing literature to explore the intricate dynamics of aesthetic appreciation in built environments.

Using Birkhoff’s scoring index, the physical attributes in terms of the preceding variables are rated on a numerical scale, and the overall Aesthetic Measure of composition is represented in the following formula:

$$\text{Aesthetic Measure (M)} = \frac{\text{Order (O)}}{\text{Complexity (C)}} \quad (1)$$

This study builds on Birkhoff’s theory and appropriates it in assessing aesthetics in Architecture, specifically in residential buildings in Davao City. The study compares ancestral and modern houses known for their distinct styles representing tradition and innovation, yet both are visually captivating. Considering this, the study generally seeks to determine the Aesthetic Measure (M) of the design elements inherent in selected residential buildings in Davao City. Specifically, it aims to determine the aesthetic score regarding Order (O) and Complexity (C) for ancestral and modern houses. It also intends to compare the computed aesthetic scores between the ancestral and contemporary homes and interpret the findings according to Birkhoff’s Aesthetic Measure. Finally, it aims to identify the most dominant characteristics of each component for both house types.

The study establishes a mathematical framework for visual evaluation, offering an objective approach to assessing residential aesthetics. Understanding prevalent design trends through this study informs future architectural endeavors. It aids architects and designers in aligning their creations with market preferences. Ultimately, it facilitates informed decision-making in residential design, contributing to the evolution of architectural practices.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

The study was conducted in Davao City, a major urban center on the island of Mindanao in the Philippines and one of the oldest and continually thriving cities in the Davao Region. The City is divided into three (3) administrative districts. It hosts a significant number of contemporary Architecture projects and serves as a home to a wide array of culturally significant heritage buildings. Hence, Davao City is a desirable study area for this research.

Research Method and Instrument

The data-gathering process encompassed several methods: visual mapping, ocular site visits, surveys, key-informant interviews, and photo documentation. Ocular site visits were conducted across various locations to map areas in Davao City where heritage houses are situated. Meanwhile, surveys and key-informant interviews were employed to collect primary data directly from respondents, such as the year the homes were constructed and other pertinent information. Photo documentation was utilized to document the residences of the study and visually capture the architectural design elements or features to be considered in assessing the overall aesthetics of the buildings. Finally, the houses’ plans were also measured using steel tape, and the plan outlines were illustrated as part of the analysis.

Research Population and Selection Criteria

The study selected two-story residential buildings in Davao City for assessment and categorized them as ancestral or modern houses. The information needed to locate the ancestral houses was primarily obtained from the Office of Museo Dabawenyo Research Department and supplemented further by Davao of the Past organization. Out of the 71 existing ancestral houses identified by the two institutions, 32 houses were chosen for study as they were representative of the study's scope, focusing exclusively on residential units. Notably, certain houses had already been demolished in the existing population of ancestral houses; three were severely dilapidated, and seven house owners declined to have their ancestral homes documented. Moreover, some remaining houses had already been converted for commercial purposes. Hence, the study was left with 32 houses, which suited the study's objectives—the years of construction of these houses ranged between the 1940s and the 1980s.

To ascertain that the number of modern houses for assessment corresponded to the number of ancestral houses, the study employed a sample size of 32. It ensured an equitable distribution for the modern houses across the three districts of Davao City. As a result, ten houses were covered in District 1, and 11 were covered in Districts 2 and 3, respectively. The selection process included only two-storey residential houses. These houses, upon ocular inspection, were determined to conform to the Modern Style of Architecture, i.e., the houses of study exhibited the following features: (1) Simple and Clean Lines, with an emphasis on simplicity, minimal ornamentation, and simple geometric shapes, (2) Incorporation of large windows to maximize natural light in its interior, and (3) Extensive use of modern materials such as concrete, steel, glass, and exposed brick or stone.

Birkhoff's Scoring Index

After photo documentation, the data gathering process proceeded to the conduct of the survey that asked the respondents to view the photos of the chosen residences and rate the aesthetics according to Birkhoff's Scoring Index. Assessment was done regarding two factors—Order (Factor 1) and Complexity (Factor 2). For the 1st Factor, the components of the Order of the chosen houses were rated using the Scoring Index in Table 1. Data for the Symmetry and Disposition of the houses were taken by evaluating their floor plans, and data for Repetition, Equilibrium, Colour Harmony, and Randomness were taken by evaluating the building elevations and perspectives.

Table 1. Scoring Index for Order (Factor 1)

Component	0	1	2	To be taken from
Symmetry (S)	Lack/no symmetry	Local symmetry	Bilateral symmetry	Floor plans
Repetition (R)	No repetition	Self-similar items that are not identically analogous but have the same outline with differences in details	Elevation with plenty of identical objects	Elevations
Equilibrium(E)	Unbalanced, unstable, or visually unsafe	Mechanical equilibrium of dynamic forms	Perfect equilibrium	Elevations
Disposition (D)	Random organization or very complicated grids	Reflect angular or complicated grids.	Conventional iron grid buildings	Floor plan
Colour harmony (H)	Use of clashing colours	Less matching colours	Uniform colors, a single color, faint, no color	Elevations, perspectives
Negative factor or Randomness (NF)	Forms that look comfortable and with the least amount of randomness	Average random of forms	Forms that look random, uncomfortable, and unstable	Elevations, perspectives

Source: Birkhoff, 1933

Likewise, for the second Factor, the components of the houses' complexity were evaluated using the Scoring Index in Table 2. Data for the houses' Form Complexity, Silhouette Differentiation, and Color Contrast were taken by evaluating their building elevations and perspectives, and data for Ornaments were taken by evaluating the houses' surface details.

Table 2. Scoring Index for Complexity (Factor 2)

Component	0	1	2	To be taken from
Form complexity (FC)	Plain masses, no curves, mass differentiation, and/or existence of iron grids	The existence of fewer curves, mass differentiation, and/or less complicated grids	The existence of items that raise tension in mind, like curves, mass differentiation, and complicated grids	Elevations, perspective
Ornaments (ORN)	For plain surfaces with no detail	Existence of a moderate level of details	The existence of regions with high levels of details	Details
Silhouette differentiation (SD)	Facades with the least number of turns	A large number of turns in the facade	Moderate number of turns in the facade	Elevations and perspective
Colour contrast (CC)	Uniform colours	Less contrasting colours	Contrasting colours	Elevations and perspective

Source: Birkhoff, 1933

Given the guides for scoring, the values generated per Component were substituted in the formula:

$$Aesthetic\ Measure\ (M) = \frac{Order\ (O)}{Complexity\ (C)} \quad (2)$$

where Order (O) is obtained through the formula:

$$ORDER\ (O) = S + R + E + D + H - N.F. \quad (3)$$

and Complexity (C) through:

$$Complexity\ (C) = FC + ORN + SD + CC. \quad (4)$$

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the scores, specifically employing the frequency of design elements to present the dataset's dominant characteristics and prevalent values. This was further complemented by interpreting the computed scores based on Birkhoff's Aesthetic Measure.

Results

The Ancestral Houses

Most ancestral houses in Davao City were constructed from 1950 to 1969, comprising twenty-one (21) houses out of the thirty-two (32) covered. The oldest house is the Oboza House, built in 1929, while

three (3) were constructed in the 1940s. Only one house was documented as having been built from 1980-1989. It is noteworthy that Davao City in the 1920s to 1930s was still under American Colonial Rule. Most American house styles were divided into four principal architectures: Ancient, Classical, Renaissance Classical, Medieval, or Modern. However, there were two primary types of domestic buildings: (1) folk houses built to provide shelter and made by the occupant or nonprofessional builders and (2) styled houses which show an influence of shapes, materials, detailing, or features that make architectural styles (Yi et al., 2020). This study, therefore, supposes that the predominant design elements of the ancestral houses that were assessed still embodied influences and design trends that emanated from the American occupation. Figure 1 introduces the Ancestral Houses covered, with each number corresponding to an item in Table 3.

Figure 1. The Ancestral Houses in Davao City Chosen for the Study

Table 3. List of Ancestral Houses of Study in Davao City

Name of Structure	Location	Year Built
1. Fornis Residence	Ponce Cor. Suazo Sts.	1940
2. Sambroso Residence	Tionko St., Poblacion, Davao City	1960s
3. Dakudao-Garcia Ancestral House	Brgy., 39-D, Davao City	1920s
4. Yrasuegi Residence	E. Quirino Ave., Brgy. 4-A	1946
5. Bason Residence	217 Rubia St., Brgy. Mintal, Davao City	1960s
6. Hechanova Residence	Mintal, Davao City	1983
7. Ulep Residence	Mintal, Davao City	1969
8. Bauson Residence	Champaca St., Mintal, Davao City	1952
9. Caburian Compound Apartments	107 A-B-C-D-E Magallanes St. Purok 1, Brgy. 39-D, Davao City	1959
10. Solono Residence	Inawayan Toril, Davao City	1961
11. Osceña Residence	V. Mapa St., Davao City	1930s
12. Ramos Residence	V. Mapa St., Davao City	1950
13. Echavez Residence	Baracatan Toril, Davao City	1950s
14. Sabanpan Residence	Brgy. 32-D, Davao City	1939
15. Malte Residence	Baracatan Toril, Davao City	1950s
16. Bautista Apartment	1017 Arellano St., Brgy. 10-A, Davao City	1940s
17. Villa-Abrille Residence	77 A. Pichon St., Poblacion, Davao City	1952
18. Gabor Residence	Jacinto Ext., Arellano St, Poblacion	1930s
19. Duplex Apartment	Rizal St., Poblacion, Davao City	1970s
20. The Big House	Juna Subd., Matina, Davao City	1930s
21. Oboza House	143 Rizal St. cor. Ponciano St., Poblacion Davao City	1929
22. Adorable Residence	385 Gumamela St., Brgy. Mintal, Davao City	1960s
23. Delos Reyes Residence	Cor. Rubia St., Brgy. Mintal, Davao City	1957
24. Dr. Layug Residence	Mintal, Davao City	1951
25. Japay Residence	Rizal St., Poblacion, Davao City	1957

26.	Bunkhouse	Bago Oshiro, Mintal, Davao City	1960s
27.	BPI Bunkhouse	Bago Oshiro, Mintal, Davao City	1960s
28.	Barsa Residence	Mt. Mayon St., Poblacion, Davao City	1960s
29.	Pancheco Residence	Bago Oshiro, Mintal, Davao City	1960s
30.	Du Residence	Rasay St. cor. Lao St., Toril, Davao City	1965
31.	Morales Residence	Bago Oshiro, Mintal, Davao City	1960s
32.	Villela Residence	Mt. Mayon St., Poblacion, Davao City	1970s

Order and Complexity of the Ancestral Houses

On the one hand, Table 4 shows the scores of the 32 Ancestral houses regarding Order, the 1st factor in the Aesthetic Measure (M) formula. The highest scorers in this factor are the Caburian Compound Apartments, Bautista Apartment, Duplex Apartment, and Adorable Residence—all of which scored 10.

Table 4. Factor 1 Scores of Ancestral Houses in Davao City per Component

Ancestral Houses of Study		Components of Order (O)						Total Score (O)
		S	R	E	D	H	NF	
1	Fornis Residence	0	1	1	2	1	0	5
2	Sambroso Residence	2	2	1	2	2	0	9
3	Dakudao-Garcia Ancestral House	1	2	1	2	2	0	8
4	Yrasuegi Residence	1	1	1	2	1	0	6
5	Bason Residence	1	2	2	2	2	0	9
6	Hechanova Residence	2	0	2	2	2	0	8
7	Ulep Residence	1	2	1	2	2	1	7
8	Bauson Residence	2	1	2	2	2	0	9
9	Caburian Compound Apartments	2	2	2	2	2	0	10
10	Solono Residence	1	2	2	2	1	0	8
11	Osceña Residence	1	2	2	2	2	0	9
12	Ramos Residence	2	2	2	2	1	0	9
13	Echavez Residence	1	1	2	2	2	0	8
14	Sabanpan Residence	1	2	2	2	2	0	9
15	Malte Residence	1	2	2	2	2	0	9
16	Bautista Apartment	2	2	2	2	2	0	10
17	Villa-Abrille Residence	2	1	1	2	1	1	6
18	Gabor Residence	2	1	2	2	1	1	7
19	Duplex Apartment	2	2	2	2	2	0	10
20	The Big House	0	1	0	2	2	0	5
21	Oboza House	1	1	1	2	2	0	7
22	Adorable Residence	2	2	2	2	2	0	10
23	Delos Reyes Residence	1	1	1	2	2	0	7
24	Dr. Layug Residence	1	1	1	2	1	0	6
25	Japay Residence	1	0	1	2	1	0	5
26	Bunkhouse	1	1	1	2	1	0	6
27	BPI Bunkhouse	1	0	1	2	2	0	6
28	Barsa Residence	1	0	0	2	0	1	2
29	Pancheco Residence	1	0	1	2	2	0	6
30	Du Residence	1	0	0	2	1	1	3
31	Morales Residence	0	0	1	2	2	0	5
32	Villela Residence	0	1	0	2	1	1	3

On the other hand, Table 5 shows the scores of the ancestral houses in terms of Complexity, the 2nd factor in the Aesthetic Measure (M) formula. The highest scorers in this factor are the Oboza House and Barsa Residence, which scored 7 and 6, respectively.

Table 5. Factor 2 Scores of Ancestral Houses in Davao City per Component

Ancestral Houses of Study		Components of Complexity (C)				Total Score
		FC	ORN	SD	CC	
1	Fornis Residence	1	1	2	1	5
2	Sambroso Residence	0	1	0	0	1
3	Dakudao-Garcia Ancestral House	0	1	0	0	1
4	Yrasuegi Residence	0	1	2	0	3
5	Bason Residence	0	0	0	0	0
6	Hechanova Residence	0	0	0	0	0
7	Ulep Residence	0	0	0	0	0
8	Bauson Residence	0	1	0	0	1
9	Caburian Compound Apartments	0	0	0	0	0
10	Solono Residence	1	0	2	1	4
11	Osceña Residence	0	1	0	0	1
12	Ramos Residence	0	0	2	1	3
13	Echavez Residence	2	0	2	0	4
14	Sabanpan Residence	0	0	0	0	0
15	Malte Residence	0	1	0	0	1
16	Bautista Apartment	0	0	0	0	0
17	Villa-Abrille Residence	1	0	1	1	3
18	Gabor Residence	0	1	1	0	2
19	Duplex Apartment	0	0	0	0	0
20	The Big House	2	0	2	1	5
21	Oboza House	2	2	2	1	7
22	Adorable Residence	0	1	0	0	1
23	Delos Reyes Residence	1	0	1	0	2
24	Dr. Layug Residence	1	1	2	1	5
25	Japay Residence	0	0	0	0	0
26	Bunkhouse	1	1	2	1	5
27	BPI Bunkhouse	1	1	2	0	4
28	Barsa Residence	1	1	2	2	6
29	Pancheco Residence	1	1	0	0	2
30	Du Residence	1	1	0	1	3
31	Morales Residence	1	1	0	0	2
32	Villela Residence	1	0	2	1	4

The Modern Houses

Most of the documented modern houses were built from 2011 to 2015. Given the year of their construction, the predominant design elements of these modern houses embodied the key features of the Modern Style of Architecture. Industrialization brought about more advanced technological and economic development. Hence, the common production materials such as concrete, iron, and glass, along with rationalism, birthed the modern style of architecture. Modern architecture could be represented by the simplicity of its form and purity of the construction system and materials used compared to the elaborate and extravagant styles of the previous architectural styles (Avila-Calle, 2023). However, modern style houses can also have expressive forms and creative designs (Yi et al., 2020). Figure 2 introduces the Modern Houses covered, with each number corresponding to an item in Table 6.

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Figure 2. The Modern Houses in Davao City chosen for Study

Table 6. List of Modern Houses of Study in Davao City

Name of Residence	Location	Year
District 1		
1. Atienza Residence	Solariega, Davao City	2010
2. Abella Residence	Solariega, Davao City	2008
3. Residence 3	Solariega, Davao City	2014
4. Domingo Residence	Bangkal, Davao City	2014
5. DOLORITO Residence	Iwha, Capili, Davao City	2015
6. Paclar Residence	Iwha, Capili, Davao City	2016
7. Mejorada Residence	Rojo St., Dacoville, Davao City	2013
8. Abdul Residence	Carmen St., Dacoville, Davao City	2015
9. Rosete Residence	Roha Subdivision, Iwha, Davao City	2007
10. Piamonte Residence	Roha Subdivision, Iwha, Davao City	2015
District 2		
11. Teodoro Residence	Nova Tierra, Pampanga, Davao City	2011
12. Briones Residence	Nova Tierra, Pampanga, Davao City	2010
13. Guevarra Residence	La Verna Residence 20, Davao City	2013
14. Monteagudo	Nova Tierra, Pampanga, Davao City	2015
15. Cabahug Residence	La Verna, Davao City	2015
16. Marikit Residence	La Verna, Davao City	2009
17. Sambo Residence	Monteverde, Davao City	2012
18. Chu Residence	Nova Tierra, Davao City	2016
19. Pioquinto Residence	La Verna, Davao City	2013
20. Residence 20	Monteverde, Davao City	2013

21.	Imbo	Monteverde, Davao City	2016
District 3			
22.	Residence 1	Meadows, Davao City	2010
23.	Ong Residence	Meadows, Davao City	2012
24.	Timor Residence	Meadows, Davao City	2006
25.	Melo Residence	Elenita Heights, Mintal, Davao City	2012
26.	Ranoa Residence	Elenita Heights, Mintal, Davao City	2013
27.	Villegas Residence	Elenita Heights, Mintal, Davao City	2005
28.	Daro Residence	Dona Rosa, Toril, Davao City	2008
29.	Gil Residence	Dona Rosa, Toril, Davao City	2010
30.	Lim Residence	Dona Rosa, Toril, Davao City	2005
31.	Fuentes Residence	Toril, Davao City	2016
32.	Bautista Residence	Dona Rosa, Toril, Davao City	2014

Order and Complexity of the Modern Houses

Table 7 shows the scores of the 32 Modern houses in terms of Order. The highest scorers in this factor are the Residence 3 and Teodoro Residence, with a score of 9, followed by Abella Residence, with a score of 8.

Table 7. Factor 1 Scores of Modern Houses in Davao City per Component

Modern Houses of Study		Components of Order (O)						Total Score (O)
		S	R	E	D	H	NF	
District 1								
1	Atienza Residence	1	0	0	2	2	0	5
2	Abella Residence	1	2	2	2	1	0	8
3	Residence 3	1	2	2	2	2	0	9
4	Domingo Residence	0	1	0	2	1	0	4
5	Dolorito Residence	1	1	1	2	2	0	7
6	Paclar Residence	1	2	1	2	2	1	7
7	Mejorada Residence	1	1	0	2	0	0	4
8	Abdul Residence	2	1	0	2	1	0	6
9	Rosete Residence	1	1	0	2	1	0	5
10	Piamonte Residence	1	0	0	2	1	0	4
District 2								
11	Teodoro Residence	2	2	2	2	1	0	9
12	Briones Residence	0	1	1	2	1	0	5
13	Guevarra Residence	1	0	1	2	1	0	5
14	Monteagudo	1	1	2	2	1	0	7
15	Cabahug Residence	1	1	0	2	1	0	5
16	Marikit Residence	1	1	1	2	1	0	6
17	Sambo Residence	2	1	0	2	1	0	6
18	Chu Residence	2	0	1	2	1	0	6
19	Pioquinto Residence	2	1	1	2	1	0	7
20	Residence 20	2	0	0	2	1	0	5
21	Villegas Residence, Monteverde	2	0	0	2	0	0	4
District 3								
22	Residence 1	1	2	1	2	1	0	7
23	Ong Residence	1	1	1	2	1	0	6
24	Timor Residence	1	1	0	2	1	0	5
25	Melo Residence	1	1	2	2	1	0	7
26	Ranoa Residence	1	0	0	2	2	0	5
27	Villegas Residence, Nova Tierra	1	1	1	0	1	0	4
28	Daro Residence	1	0	0	2	1	0	4
29	Gil Residence	2	0	2	2	1	1	6
30	Lim Residence	1	0	0	2	1	0	4
31	Fuentes Residence	0	0	0	2	1	1	2
32	Bautista Residence	2	1	1	2	1	0	7

Meanwhile, Table 8 shows the scores of the modern houses in terms of Complexity. The highest scorers in this factor are the residences of Domingo, Mejorada, Abdul, Rosete, Piamonte, Cabahug, Sambo, and Chu, as well as Residence 20—all of which scored 6.

Table 8. Factor 2 Scores of Modern Houses in Davao City per Component

Modern Houses of Study		Components of Complexity (C)				Total Score
		FC	ORN	SD	CC	
District 1						
1	Atienza Residence	1	0	2	0	3
2	Abella Residence	0	0	0	2	2
3	Residence 3	1	0	2	1	4
4	Domingo Residence	2	0	2	2	6
5	Dolorito Residence	0	0	2	1	3
6	Paclar Residence	1	0	2	0	3
7	Mejorada Residence	2	0	2	2	6
8	Abdul Residence	1	1	2	2	6
9	Rosete Residence	2	0	2	2	6
10	Piamonte Residence	2	0	2	2	6
District 2						
11	Teodoro Residence	0	1	2	0	3
12	Briones Residence	1	0	2	2	5
13	Guevarra Residence	1	0	2	1	4
14	Monteagudo	0	0	2	2	4
15	Cabahug Residence	2	0	2	2	6
16	Marikit Residence	1	0	0	1	2
17	Sambo Residence	1	1	2	2	6
18	Chu Residence	1	1	2	2	6
19	Pioquinto Residence	1	0	2	1	4
20	Residence 20	2	0	2	2	6
21	Villegas Residence, Monteverde	1	0	1	2	4
District 3						
22	Residence 1	1	0	2	1	4
23	Ong Residence	1	0	0	2	3
24	Timor Residence	1	0	0	1	2
25	Melo Residence	1	0	2	1	4
26	Ranoa Residence	2	0	2	0	4
27	Villegas Residence, Nova Tierra	1	1	0	1	3
28	Daro Residence	2	0	2	1	5
29	Gil Residence	0	0	0	1	1
30	Lim Residence	0	0	0	1	1
31	Fuentes Residence	2	0	1	2	5
32	Bautista Residence	1	1	0	2	4

Aesthetic Measure of Ancestral Houses vis-à-vis Modern Houses in Davao City

Table 9. Aesthetic Measure of Ancestral and Modern Houses in Davao City

Ancestral Houses of Study		M	Modern Houses of Study		M
1	Fornis Residence		Atienza Residence		
2	Sambroso Residence		Abella Residence		
3	Dakudao-Garcia Ancestral House		Residence 3		
4	Yrasuegi Residence		Domingo Residence		
5	Bason Residence		Dolorito Residence		
6	Hechanova Residence		Paclar Residence		
7	Ulep Residence		Mejorada Residence		
8	Bauson Residence		Abdul Residence		

9	Caburian Compound Apartments		Rosete Residence	
10	Solono Residence		Piamonte Residence	
11	Osceña Residence		Teodoro Residence	
12	Ramos Residence		Briones Residence	
13	Echavez Residence		Guevarra Residence	
14	Sabanpan Residence		Monteagudo	
15	Malte Residence		Cabahug Residence	
16	Bautista Apartment		Marikit Residence	
17	Villa-Abrille Residence		Sambo Residence	
18	Gabor Residence		Chu Residence	
19	Duplex Apartment		Pioquinto Residence	
20	The Big House		Residence 20	
21	Oboza House		Villegas Residence, Monteverde	
22	Adorable Residence		Residence 1	
23	Delos Reyes Residence		Ong Residence	
24	Dr. Layug Residence		Timor Residence	
25	Japay Residence		Melo Residence	
26	Bunkhouse		Ranoa Residence	
27	BPI Bunkhouse		Villegas Residence, Nova Tierra	
28	Barsa Residence		Daro Residence	
29	Pancheco Residence		Gil Residence	
30	Du Residence		Lim Residence	
31	Morales Residence		Fuentes Residence	
32	Villela Residence		Bautista Residence	

Discussion

The interpretation of the computed Aesthetic Measure (M) emanated from Birkhoff's theory and, as such, was done in the following manner:

Lower order and Higher Complexity: $0.125 \leq M \leq 1$ building with poor aesthetics and with a high level of excitement

Higher order and Lower Complexity: $2 \leq M \leq 4$ Fairly Aesthetic Building with an average level of excitement

Order is much higher than Complexity: $4 \leq M \leq 10$ Highly Ordered structure with the least number of details or complexity.

Order equals Complexity: $M = 1$ highly ordered structure with high excitement and complexity (Most Favorable)

Computed Aesthetic Measure

Figure 3. Summary Interpretation of the Computed Aesthetic Measure (M) of Ancestral Houses

According to the pie graph in Figure 3, the highest percentage (47%) is the interpretation that Order in Ancestral Houses is Much Higher than Complexity ($4 \leq M \leq 10$). This means the majority of the respondents perceived the ancestral houses as highly ordered structures with the least number of details or complexity. It only shows that Heritage Houses focuses more on Order than Complexity.

Figure 4. Summary Interpretation of the Computed Aesthetic Measure (M) of Modern Houses

Meanwhile, the pie graph in Figure 4 shows that the highest percentage (53%) is the interpretation that modern houses are moderately higher in Order and lower in Complexity. This means that Modern Houses, like the Ancestral Houses, focus on Order and consider the Complexity factor. In other words, modern houses are perceived to have fair aesthetics that offer an average excitement level.

Characteristics of Ancestral and Modern Houses in Davao City

The scoring of each component of the two factors, Order (O) and Complexity (C), was conducted using Birkhoff's Scoring Index, previously presented in Table 1. The scoring involved assigning ratings of two (2), one (1), or zero (0) to each component. The resulting scores correspond to specific assessments (*refer to Table 1*), which will be elaborated further in subsequent narratives.

Table 5. Summary Frequencies of the Components of Order of Ancestral Houses vis-à-vis Modern Houses

Components of Order:	Total number of houses for each score (Ancestral Houses)			Total number of houses for each score (Modern Houses)		
	0	1	2	0	1	2
Symmetry	4	18	10	3	20	9
Repetition	7	12	13	11	16	5
Equilibrium	4	13	15	4	13	15
Disposition	0	1	31	15	11	31
Colour Harmony	3	10	19	3	24	5
Negative Factor	25	6	0	29	3	0

Significant insights were gained by examining the frequencies in the dataset concerning the factor of Order presented in Table 5. These observations shed light on the specific characteristics contributing to the overall aesthetic value of the houses covered. For instance, in the component of Symmetry, bilateral

symmetry emerged as the dominant characteristic for both Ancestral and Modern Houses. This means that both house types exhibited a balanced and symmetrical design. Secondly, when considering the component of Repetition, Ancestral houses were found to have façade elevations with plenty of similar items. In contrast, modern houses showcased elevations with self-similar features that share the same plan outline but differ in minor details. In terms of Equilibrium, ancestral houses demonstrated perfect equilibrium, or a visually balanced and stable design, whereas the modern houses covered and exhibited façade elevations that were visually unbalanced. Subsequently, both house types were characterized by conventional iron grid buildings when considering the disposition component. Regarding Colour Harmony, ancestral houses predominantly featured uniform colors, while modern houses exhibited fewer matching colors. In terms of Randomness or the component of Negative Factor, both house types possessed building forms that were perceived as comfortable with a lesser amount of Randomness.

Table 6. Summary Frequencies of the Components of Complexity of Ancestral Houses vis-à-vis Modern Houses

Components of Order:	Total number of houses for each score (Ancestral Houses)			Total number of houses for each score (Modern Houses)		
	0	1	2	0	1	2
Form complexity (FC)	17	12	3	4	17	9
Ornaments (ORN)	14	17	1	26	6	0
Silhouette differentiation (SD)	17	4	11	8	2	22
Colour contrast (CC)	21	10	31	4	11	17

As to the Complexity factor shown in Table 6, firstly, the Form Complexity of the house types revealed that ancestral houses were associated with plain building masses. In contrast, modern houses displayed fewer curves and differences in building mass. In terms of Ornaments, heritage houses exhibited moderate details, whereas modern houses displayed plain surfaces. Subsequently, silhouette differentiation indicated that ancestral houses had facades with the least number of turns, while modern houses had many turns. Lastly, when considering Colour Contrast, ancestral houses generally displayed uniform colors, while modern houses had contrasting colors.

An analysis of the said components revealed that Ancestral Houses exhibited higher Order than Complexity, suggesting a greater emphasis on a well-structured design with fewer details. On the other hand, Modern Houses displayed a moderately higher Order and lower Complexity, indicating a fairly aesthetic building with an average level of excitement.

Conclusion

This study sought to determine the Aesthetic Measure (M) of the design elements inherent in selected residential buildings in Davao City. Specifically, it aimed to quantify the aesthetic scores of Order (O) and Complexity (C) for ancestral and modern houses, interpret these scores using Birkhoff's Aesthetic Measure, and compare the results between the two-house types. Furthermore, the study identified the dominant characteristics of each component that contributed to the overall aesthetics of the residential buildings.

The findings indicate a strong preference for bilateral symmetry in floor plans, balanced proportions in building elevations, and a moderate level of detail complexity in both ancestral and modern houses. These characteristics suggest that visual harmony and proportionality are fundamental considerations in residential aesthetics. The emphasis on symmetry and balanced proportions aligns with established architectural principles that associate these attributes with a sense of order, stability, and visual appeal. Additionally, the study highlights the role of color in enhancing aesthetic interest, as uniform colors

contribute to a timeless and classic appeal, while contrasting colors introduce a more contemporary and dynamic visual identity. By understanding these aesthetic preferences, architects and designers can create residential buildings that resonate with the visual expectations of homeowners and potential buyers. The integration of these findings into architectural design processes can enhance the marketability of residential structures while preserving essential aesthetic qualities that contribute to a well-designed urban landscape.

A potential implication of this study is the need for a more detailed understanding of how aesthetic preferences influence architectural trends and urban design choices. Given this, future research should incorporate a broader range of building typologies beyond residential structures to determine whether similar aesthetic patterns emerge in commercial, institutional, and mixed-use developments. Expanding the application of Birkhoff's Aesthetic Measure to various aspects of architecture and design—such as interior spaces, façades, and streetscapes—could provide a more comprehensive evaluation of aesthetic preferences across different contexts. Furthermore, incorporating perceptual studies through surveys or eye-tracking technology may offer deeper insights into how individuals visually engage with architectural elements, further refining the understanding of aesthetic appeal in the built environment.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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